

A DESCRIPTIVE EXPLORATION OF HOW OCCUPATIONAL SELF-EFFICACY AFFECTS ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT AMONG TEACHER EDUCATORS

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Abstract

The study aimed to assess the extent to which Occupational Self-Efficacy (OSE) can predict Organizational Commitment (OC) among teacher educators in the Murshidabad district. Fifteen teacher training institutes were chosen, and 150 teacher educators were selected via simple random sampling. The present investigation was structured around two hypotheses and to test them, two instruments were used: an Organizational Commitment Scale for Teacher Educators created by the researcher, and the Occupational Self-Efficacy Scale developed by Pethe, Chaudhiri, and Dhar (2022). A total of 150 teacher educators were chosen through simple random sampling, and data analysis involved Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC) and Stepwise Multiple Regression (SMR). The researcher determined a linear correlation between OC and OSE. OSE was found to be the leading variable influencing OC, with its contribution representing 3.6% of the variance (Ali, 2024).

Keywords- *Organizational Commitment, Occupational Self-efficacy and Teacher Educators*

1. Introduction

Organizational commitment's conceptual foundations require us to explore the bond between people and the institutions they belong to. In both management studies and behavioural sciences, this commitment is frequently recognised as central to how individuals interact with their organisations. In the realms of organisational behaviour and human resources management, researchers show great interest in how employees' attitudes toward OSE relate to their levels of OC. This study seeks to determine whether OSE has a relationship with OC, and to assess the extent to which it can serve as a strong predictor of that commitment.

Commitment to an organization is characterized by a strong willingness to stay on-board, a feeling of belonging, and a motivation to invest personal effort on its behalf. The construct typically divides into three parts: affective, continuance, and normative commitment. The affective aspect denotes emotional attachment; continuance refers to rational calculations about the losses that might come if one departs; and normative refers to an inner sense of duty or obligation. When someone feels normative commitment, they perceive a duty to stay with their organisation. Occupational self-efficacy refers to the confidence an individual has in fulfilling the responsibilities of their vocation. The findings of this article indicate that occupational self-efficacy correlates positively with organisational commitment, and also plays a predictive role in shaping teacher educators' commitment to their organisation. Agarwal and Mishra (2016) also attempted to explore the degree to which OC among revenue personnel is significantly predicted by self-efficacy and the relationship of the two. The study implied that OC was significantly correlated with self-efficacy and self-efficacy significantly affects OC among revenue employees.

2. Conceptual Framework

2.1. Occupational Self-Efficacy

Occupational self-efficacy refers to the degree to which individuals believe they can successfully execute the tasks required in a particular task or field of interest. The idea of self-efficacy was first articulated by Albert Bandura in 1977 as part of his social learning (later social cognitive) theory. Rooted in human social cognition research, Bandura's early work emphasized humans' extraordinary ability to use symbols and mental representations in learning and action.

Occupational self-efficacy is the belief in one's ability to perform the responsibilities associated with a given profession. Bandura (1994) describes this construct as one's confidence in one's capabilities. Consequently, individuals high in self-efficacy treat unfamiliar tasks as challenges to tackle, whereas those low in self-efficacy tend to avoid such tasks, perceiving risk in stepping out of their comfort zones. Maddux (2002) emphasizes that self-efficacy is not hereditary; it's about perceptions of how well one can leverage their skills and competence under specific circumstances to reach desired results.

Bandura (1997) defines self-efficacy "as faith in one's capabilities to organize and execute the course of action required to manage a prospective situation. It constitutes a faith about one's ability to fulfil a particular task pattern."

Omrod (2006) defined Occupational self-efficacy “as the one’s own capacity to perform the given tasks and reach organizational goals.”

Mitchell et al. (1994) defined Occupational self-efficacy “as the ability to acquire more skills”.

2.2. Organizational Commitment

In recent years, researchers in organisational behaviour and education have shown growing interest in organisational commitment, making it one of the most examined constructs related to one’s job. Scholars are increasingly investigating both its antecedents and its outcomes. Numerous studies have linked OC to favourable outcomes—higher job performance, better attendance, more satisfied employees, and reduced employee turnover (Shore & Martin, 1989). More recently, reviews suggest that organisations with committed employees tend to outperform rivals and have higher survival prospects compared to organisations whose workforce is less committed (Aityan & Gupta, 2012). As a result, committed personnel are widely regarded as key organisational assets that should be retained.

Several scholars have conceptualized OC as the degree to which employees feel psychologically attached to their organisation. Jaros et al. (1993) identify three components: affective commitment, which involves emotional attachment and identification with the organisation; continuance commitment, which is based on the perceived costs associated with leaving; and normative commitment, which stems from a sense of obligation to remain. In a similar vein, Mayer and Schoorman (1992) discuss value commitment, where individuals are dedicated to the organisation's principles and objectives, and continuance commitment, which is influenced by the perceived necessity of staying due to external constraints.

OC encompasses an individual's psychological attachment to their workplace. Sheldon (1971) highlights that this commitment is a reflection of one's sense of belonging to the organization. Meyer and Allen (1997) further elaborate, suggesting that this commitment is characterized by emotional attachment, influencing an employee's decision to remain with the organization. Beyond mere interpersonal relationships, commitment involves the active investment of personal energy and cognitive resources. It reflects a person's socio-psychological bond to their group or organization, aligning with its objectives and core values.

OC among employees means that they are ready to work hard for the organisation, intend to stay with it over time, and understand its central aims and foundational principles. (Porter and Lawler, 1968).

O'Reilly, (1989) defined it as “an individual’s psychological bond to the organization, including a sense of job involvement, loyalty and belief in the values of the organization.”

“Organizational commitment is a result of the perception of benefit associated with staying in and the perception of the cost associated with leaving from an organization” (Kanter, 1968).

2.3. Teacher Educators

A person employed in an official capacity for the purpose of guiding and directing the learning experiences of pupils or students in an educational institution, whether Government or private may be termed as a teacher (Dictionary of Education, C.V.Good, 1973). In this study, teachers teaching in Teacher Training Institutions are considered as teacher educators.

3. Statement of the Problem

The problem is formally stated as “A Descriptive Exploration of How Occupational Self-efficacy affects Organizational Commitment among Teacher Educators”

4. Operational Definitions of the Key Terms

4.1. Organizational Commitment

Morrow (1993) defined organizational commitment as “an attitude that reflects feelings such as attachment, identification and loyalty to the organization as an object of commitment.”

Porter and Lawler (1968) viewed organizational commitment as the willingness of an employee to exert high levels of effort on behalf of the organization, a strong desire to stay with the organization, and an acceptance of its major goals and values.

In the present study, operational organizational commitment is considered as the total marks that the teacher educators obtained on the organizational commitment scale developed by the researcher.

4.2. Occupational Self Efficacy

Occupational self-efficacy is how much a person believes they can perform the tasks in a particular career or vocational pursuit.

In this study, operationally, occupational self-efficacy is considered as the total marks that the teacher educators obtained on the occupational self-efficacy scale developed by Sanjyot Pethe, Sushama Chaudhuri, and Upinder Dhar (2022).

4.3. Teacher Educators

In an educational institution, whether public or private, anyone formally employed to oversee and direct students’ learning experiences may be referred to as a teacher (C. V. Good, 1973).

For the purposes of this study, those teaching within Teacher Training Institutions are regarded as teacher-educators.

5. Objectives of the Study

- i) To study the relationship between OC and OSE among teacher educators.
- ii) To find out the effect of OSE on OC among teachers educators.

1. Hypothesis of the Study

H₀₁ There will be no significant relationship between OC and OSE among teacher educators.

H₀₂ There will be no significant effect of OSE on OC among teacher educators.

6. Methodology

In conducting the study, a descriptive design was employed with the use of the descriptive survey method. This design was appropriate as it enables investigation of both the existing relationship between the independent and dependent variables and how the independent variable affects the dependent variable, through data gathered by questionnaire.

6.1. Population and Sample

The population for the study comprises every teacher educator working in governmental or private teacher-training facilities in Murshidabad district. The investigator selected 15 institutions and then obtained responses from 150 teacher educators. The institutions were chosen purposively and within them the questionnaires were distributed randomly.

Figure 1: Sample of the Study

- Occupational Self-Efficacy Scale, which was developed by Sanjyot Pethe, Sushama Chaudhiri, and Upinder Dhar (2022)

Figure 4: Tools for Data Collection

6.3. Statistical Technique

To analyze the data, the researcher applied stepwise multiple regression techniques and calculated correlation coefficients.

7. Analysis and Interpretation of the Data

Objective-i

To study the relationship between the criterion variable i.e. organizational commitment and predictive variables i.e. occupational self-efficacy and job satisfaction of teacher educators working in urban areas.

For the purpose of fulfilling Objective 1, the researcher proposed the following null hypothesis:

H₀₁

“There will be no significant relationship between the criterion variable i.e. organizational commitment and predictive variables i.e. occupational self-efficacy and job satisfaction of teacher educators working in urban areas”.

With the goal of fulfilling the above mentioned objective, the study treated OC as the criterion variable while OSE acted as the predictive variable. The relationship was then explored applying the Pearson product-moment correlation.

The tabular presentation shows the correlation results between the criterion variable and the predictive variables for the sample of teacher educators.

Table 1: Correlation between the Criterion and Predictive Variables among Teacher Educators Working in Urban Areas.

Predictive Variables	Criterion Variable (Organizational Commitment)
	Urban (N= 150)
Occupational Self-Efficacy	.190*

From the table above, it is clear that the correlation coefficient between OC and OSE for the urban sample is significant at the .05 level.

Figure 5: The Scatter Plot of Coefficient Correlation between OC and OSE of Teacher Educators Working in Urban Areas.

The Pearson correlation between OC and OSE among teacher-educators was found to be $r = .190$ ($p < .05$), thereby achieving significance at the .05 threshold. The upward-sloping line in Figure 5 and the dispersion of data points around the best-fit line further endorse the positive association. These findings suggest that as teacher-educators' OSE increases, their OC also tends to rise.

From the above discussion, it is evident that a significant correlation exists between OC and OSE among teacher educators at the 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the null hypothesis H_01 stating "There will be no significant relationship between organisational commitment and the predictive variables (occupational self-efficacy and job satisfaction) among teacher educators," is accepted.

Objective -ii

To find out the effect of predictive variables i.e. occupational self-efficacy and job satisfaction on criterion variable i.e. organizational commitment of teachers educators working in urban areas.

To address the aforementioned objective, the researcher proposed the following null hypothesis:

H_02

There will be no significant effect of predictive variables i.e. occupational self-efficacy on criterion variable i.e. organizational Commitment of teachers educators.

To examine the hypothesis described above, the researcher employed a stepwise multiple linear regression approach. The relevant dataset is provided in the table below.

Table 2: Model Summary of Stepwise Regression Analysis

Predictive Variables	R	R ²	R ² Change	F- Change	P- Value
OSE	.190	.0337	.037	5.457*	.022

From Table 2 above we see that 'R' in the model denotes the correlation between the actual and predicted values of the dependent variable, which in this case is 0.190. This indicates that the model's prediction of OC for teacher educators based on the predictor variable OSE has a correlation of 0.190 with the OC reported by the teacher educators.

Table 3: summary of ANOVA for Regression Analysis

Source of Variation	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	P- value
Regression	939.145	1	939.145	5.457*	.022
Residual	25471.817	148	172.108		
Total	26410.961	149			

Figure 6: Percentage Contribution of Predictive Variables on the Criterion Variable i.e. OC of Teacher Educators Working in Urban Areas

In this model, R^2 indicates how much of the dependent variable’s variance is predicted by the independent variable(s) Table 5 shows that the regression model with one predictor explains 3.6% of the variance ($R^2 = .037$, $F = 5.457$, $p < 0.05$). Hence, results from Table 2 and Table 3 identify OSE as a meaningful predictor of OC among urban teacher educators. Moreover, Table-2 highlights OSE as the primary influential variable behind OC, with its contribution amounting to 3.6% (i.e. = R^2 Change = .037, $F = 5.457$, $p < 0.05$).

Table 4: Coefficient Regression Analysis

Predictive variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t- Value	P- Value
	B	Std. Error	β		
(Constant)	95.240	10.416		9.145**	.000
OSE	.351	.151	.190	2.337*	.022

According to Table 6, the standardized coefficient for the predictor (i.e., OSE) is positive and statistically significant at the 5% level. Specifically, the table indicates that OSE ($\beta = 0.190$, $t = 2.337$, $p < 0.05$) possesses strong predictive strength for the OC of teacher-educators. Thus a one unit increase in OSE corresponds to a 0.190-unit rise in OC. In other words, this predictor is both positive and significant, meaning that increases in OSE lead to meaningful increases in OC.

The analysis indicates that OSE significantly affects OC at the 0.05 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis “There will be no significant effect of predictive variables i.e., occupational self-efficacy on criterion variable i.e., organizational commitment of teachers educators” is accepted. It means that for the teacher educators predictive variable can be used to predict their OC. This implies that for teacher-educators, OSE can indeed serve as a predictor of their OC, and the relationship observed cannot be attributed to random chance.

8. Findings

The findings indicate that occupational self-efficacy and OC are positively and significantly correlated ($r=.190$, $p<.05$) for teacher educators demonstrating a medium strength.

The study found that occupational self-efficacy significantly influences OC among teacher-educators with the predictor accounting for 3.6% of the total variance in commitment ($R^2=.037$, $F= 5.457$, $p< 0.05$).

9. Conclusion

Findings of the study lead us to conclude that OSE emerged as the most significant contributing variable in influencing the OC as its contribution was 3.6% and OSE and OC are positively and significantly correlated for teacher educators demonstrating a medium strength.

10. Implications

10.1. Teacher-training programmes must support teacher educators in cultivating strong OSE, given its emergence as a key factor in teacher education. To foster greater OSE among faculty, institutions should create a nurturing environment and help individuals recognise and harness their personal strengths.

10.2. We need to take more proactive measures to bolster teachers’ OSE since it plays a crucial role in their OC and thus supports improved teaching and learning. With higher self-efficacy, teacher educators are more likely to be effective, responsive to fresh ideas, willing to take risks in teaching practices, and deeply committed to their roles.

10.3. To strengthen the quality of the M.Ed. programme, the curriculum should embed the notion of OSE. Accordingly, it is recommended that institutions preparing teachers should integrate OSE into their curricula so as to boost the capabilities of those training teachers.

10.4. Efforts must be made by policymakers and administrative leaders to boost teacher-educators’ OSE, as well as their teaching skills and subject knowledge, since the present study revealed that teacher-educators differ in occupational self-efficacy based on gender,

location and experience. Accordingly, a variety of targeted initiatives such as intervention programmes, workshops, conferences, seminars and faculty-development events should be organised to enhance both their self-efficacy and requisite professional skills.

11. Suggestions for the Further Study

11.1. Since this research was restricted to the Murshidabad district of West Bengal, its findings may be further validated by expanding to other regions of the country. Accordingly, it is recommended that comparable studies be undertaken in other districts and areas across the nation.

11.2. Besides teacher educators, future studies could include principals, administrators, elementary, middle and high school teachers, faculty from public and private colleges, and university instructors since the present study's sample was restricted only to teacher educators.

11.3. Future research of this kind could benefit from using broader geographic areas, more varied populations, and a wider range of data-collection techniques and methodologies.

11.4. Since the current study considered only two independent variables, it is recommended that future research can examine other psychological factors that could influence organizational commitment among teacher educators. This approach would help identify additional determinants of their commitment.

11.5. In this study, only gender, institution location, and experience were considered as demographic variables. It is advisable for subsequent studies to include other demographic factors like type of institution, academic qualifications, marital status, professional designations, and research experience.

11.6. In this study, a quantitative methodology is employed. Future investigations should consider adopting a mixed-methods approach, blending quantitative and qualitative methods to gain a more holistic understanding.

12. List of Abbreviations

OC Organizational Commitment

OSE Occupational Self-Efficacy

PCC Pearson Correlation Coefficient

SRM Stepwise Multiple Regression

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